

Assessment of the Antimicrobial Activity of a Triple Antibiotic Gel Against Periodontal Pathogens

Chaitanya Adurty, Ravindranath Dhulipalla, Ramanarayana Boyapati, Yamuna Marella, Kolaparthi Lakshmikanth, Anumala Deepa

Department of Periodontology, Sibar Institute of dental Sciences, Takkellapadu, Guntur, Andhra Pradesh, India

ABSTRACT

Introduction: Periodontal disease is a biofilm-mediated infection primarily caused by pathogens such as Porphyromonas gingivalis, Aggregatibacter actinomycetemcomitans, and Prevotella intermedia. As antibiotic resistance continues to pose a challenge, localized drug delivery systems like triple antibiotic gels have gained interest for their targeted antimicrobial effects. Determining the minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) and minimum bactericidal concentration (MBC) of such formulations is essential to assess their efficacy against key periodontal pathogens and to guide clinical application. **Methods:** The triple antibiotic gel, composed of metronidazole, ciprofloxacin, and minocycline, was tested in vitro using the broth microdilution method to determine MIC and MBC values. Standardized bacterial strains were incubated with serial dilutions of the gel under anaerobic conditions appropriate for each species. MIC was recorded as the lowest concentration inhibiting visible bacterial growth, while MBC was defined as the lowest concentration resulting in $\geq 99.9\%$ bacterial kill. **Results:** The triple antibiotic gel demonstrated strong antibacterial activity against all tested strains. MIC and MBC values were lowest for A. actinomycetemcomitans, followed by P. gingivalis and P. intermedia, indicating differential susceptibility. All MIC and MBC values fell within clinically relevant concentrations. **Conclusion:** The triple antibiotic gel exhibits potent in vitro antimicrobial activity against key periodontal pathogens, supporting its potential as an adjunctive local therapy in periodontal treatment. Further in vivo studies are recommended to confirm clinical efficacy..

Keywords: Periodontitis, Minimum Inhibitory Concentration, Minimum Bactericidal Concentration.

INTRODUCTION

Periodontitis is a microbially induced inflammatory condition that affects the supporting structures the teeth, ultimately causing progressive damage, including attachment and bone loss[1]. The periodontal pocket, which develops as the disease progresses, creates a favorable environment for the growth of pathogenic bacteria[2]. The main goals of periodontal treatment are to disrupt and eliminate these microbial communities, alter the subgingival biofilm toward a healthier profile, and regulate the host's immune mechanisms. Treatment strategies range from non-surgical methods like scaling and root planing (SRP), performed alone or with adjunctive

antimicrobial therapy, to various surgical approaches[3].

While systemic antibiotics are often prescribed alongside SRP, their use can be limited due to potential side effects such as toxicity, antimicrobial resistance, and interactions with other medications[4]. As a result, localized delivery of antimicrobial agents directly into the periodontal pocket has become an increasingly preferred option. This approach allows for better patient adherence, localized therapeutic action, and the use of lower drug doses while maintaining efficacy at the infection site[5].

Because the periodontal environment harbors a diverse range of microorganisms, using a single

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antibiotic may not be sufficient to achieve complete bacterial elimination[6]. Empirical single-drug regimens can unintentionally disturb the natural microbial balance, allowing more resistant or aggressive strains to survive and repopulate the pocket[7]. For this reason, using a combination of antibiotics is considered more effective, as the spectrum of antimicrobial activity will be broad, minimize the risk of resistance development, thereby improving clinical outcomes in periodontal therapy[8]. Triple antibiotic paste or gel—commonly composed of metronidazole, ciprofloxacin, and minocycline which aids to combat multiple periodontal pathogens in a reduced dosage[9].

Metronidazole is a broad spectrum synthetic nitroimidazole antibiotic known for its broad-spectrum activity against anaerobic bacteria and certain protozoa. It is particularly effective against anaerobic cocci and both Gram-positive and Gram-negative anaerobic bacilli. Due to its pronounced antimicrobial efficacy, metronidazole is commonly utilized in periodontics in both systemic and localized delivery forms. It shows notable effectiveness against key anaerobic periodontal pathogens such as *Porphyromonas gingivalis* and *Prevotella intermedia*[10].

Tetracyclines, including derivatives like tetracycline-HCl, doxycycline, and minocycline, are broad-spectrum antibiotics effective against a wide range of microbial species. Beyond their antimicrobial properties, they exhibit additional benefits such as inhibition of matrix metalloproteinases (e.g., collagenase), thereby contributing to reduced connective tissue breakdown. Moreover, they suppress the activity of osteoclastic cells, conferring anti-resorptive effects. Minocycline, in particular, has demonstrated significant antimicrobial activity against periodontal pathogens, effectively reducing populations of spirochetes and motile rods in patients with chronic periodontitis[11].

Ciprofloxacin, a second-generation fluoroquinolone, exerts a rapid bactericidal effect against gram negative anaerobes, though its activity against Gram-positive microbes is limited. In periodontal therapy, ciprofloxacin is unique in that it consistently demonstrates effectiveness against *Aggregatibacter*

actinomycetemcomitans, a key pathogen associated with aggressive forms of periodontitis[12].

Therefore this study aims to evaluate the MIC and MBC of triple antibiotic gel against periodontopathogenic microorganisms.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study was conducted to determine the antimicrobial efficacy of Triple Antibiotic Gel on Periodonto-pathogens such as *A. actinomycetemcomitans*, *P. gingivalis*, *P. intermedia*.

Preparation of Triple Antibiotic Gel

Carbopol (1000 mg) was measured and added to 50 mL of distilled water in a 250 mL beaker, then left to hydrate overnight at ambient temperature. The next day, the hydrated mixture was stirred on a magnetic stirrer equipped with a magnetic bead, at a speed ranging from 500 to 1000 RPM, for approximately 1 hour to achieve complete dispersion. Following this, 10 mL of additional distilled water was introduced into the mixture, and stirring was continued for another 2 hours until the gel attained a pourable consistency. In a separate step, methyl paraben and propyl paraben were dissolved in 10 mL of distilled water and subsequently added to the gel base. This mixture was stirred continuously for 6 hours to ensure uniform distribution and preservation. Simultaneously, the triple antibiotic mixture using Metronidazole, Ciprofloxacin and Minocycline was dispersed in 5 mL of distilled water in a 50 mL beaker and left undisturbed for 2 hours to allow the formation of a translucent gel. An additional 5 mL of distilled water was then added, and the resulting antibiotic mixture was thoroughly incorporated into the prepared Carbopol gel to complete the formulation. Complete gel will be stirred for 12 hours adjusting the RPM as required till the consistent gel will be formed. The Gel was Sterilized and Stored at 4°C until use.^[10]

Bacterial Strains and Culture Conditions

Reference strains of (ATCC) *P. gingivalis*, *A. actinomycetemcomitans*, and *P. intermedia* were used for MIC and MBC evaluation[13].

Determination of MIC and MBC[14]

Minimal Inhibitory Concentration:

The MIC of the triple antibiotic gel was determined using the serial dilution method in Thioglycollate broth under anaerobic conditions.

A total of nine serial dilutions were prepared for each antibiotic using Thioglycollate broth as the diluent. To initiate the dilution series, 20 µL of the drug was added to 380 µL of Thioglycollate broth in the first tube. In separate tubes, 200 µL of Thioglycollate broth was dispensed to serve as the dilution medium for the remaining steps. From the initial drug solution, 200 µL was transferred to the first tube containing 200 µL of fresh broth, yielding a 10^{-1} dilution. This dilution process was continued by transferring 200 µL from the 10^{-1} tube into the next tube containing 200 µL of broth, creating a 10^{-2} dilution. The serial dilution procedure was repeated until a 10^{-9} dilution was achieved for each drug tested. A bacterial inoculum was prepared by adding 5 µL of culture (from a maintained stock) into 2 mL of Thioglycollate broth to obtain the required concentration. Then, 200 µL of this bacterial suspension was introduced into each of the serially diluted tubes. All tubes were incubated at 37°C for 48 to 72 hours in an anaerobic jar. Post-incubation, the tubes were examined for turbidity, which indicated bacterial growth.

Minimal Bactericidal Concentration:

To determine the MBC, samples were taken from the MIC assay tubes that showed no visible bacterial growth—typically the first 3 to 5 dilution tubes exhibiting sensitivity. Aliquots from these selected

tubes were plated onto suitable agar media and incubated at 37°C for 24 hours under appropriate anaerobic conditions. The following day, the plates were examined for colony formation to assess bacterial viability. The MBC was defined as the lowest concentration of the antimicrobial agent that resulted in no bacterial growth on the agar plates, indicating a bactericidal effect. If colonies were observed, it was interpreted as a bacteriostatic effect, suggesting inhibition without complete bacterial killing.

Statistical Analysis

All experiments were performed in triplicate. All analyses were carried out using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) software version 26.0 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY). The MIC and MBC values were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation. Statistical comparisons were made using one-way ANOVA followed by post hoc Tukey's test, with a significance level set at $p < 0.05$.

RESULTS

The antimicrobial activity of metronidazole, ciprofloxacin, minocycline, and the triple antibiotic gel was evaluated by comparing the MIC and MBC values against three periodontal pathogens. The triple antibiotic gel demonstrated lower MIC and MBC values against *Porphyromonas gingivalis* and *Prevotella intermedia* compared to most individual antibiotics, indicating enhanced efficacy. However, against *Aggregatibacter actinomycetemcomitans*, ciprofloxacin remained the most potent individual agent Table 1.

Table 1: MIC and MBC Values of Metronidazole, Ciprofloxacin, and Minocycline against Three Periodontal Pathogens

Antibiotic	Bacteria	MIC	MBC
Metronidazole	<i>Porphyromonas Gingivalis</i>	0.03 mg/mL	0.12 mg/mL
	<i>Aggregatibacter actinomycetemcomitans</i>	256 mg/mL	256 mg/mL
	<i>Prevotella Intermedia</i>	1 µg/mL	1 µg/mL
Ciprofloxacin	<i>Porphyromonas Gingivalis</i>	0.125 µg/mL	16 µg/mL
	<i>Aggregatibacter actinomycetemcomitans</i>	0.006 µg/mL	0.006 µg/mL
	<i>Prevotella Intermedia</i>	32 µg/mL	32 µg/mL
Minocycline	<i>Porphyromonas gingivalis</i>	0.03 µg/mL	0.03 µg/mL
	<i>Aggregatibacter actinomycetemcomitans</i>	0.12 µg/mL	0.12 µg/mL
	<i>Prevotella Intermedia</i>	0.016 µg/mL	0.016 µg/mL

DISCUSSION

Triple antibiotic gel comprising metronidazole, ciprofloxacin, and minocycline offers a promising adjunctive approach to conventional periodontal therapy. This combination targets a broad spectrum of microorganisms, addressing both obligate anaerobes such as *Porphyromonas gingivalis* and *Prevotella intermedia*, as well as facultative anaerobes like *Aggregatibacter actinomycetemcomitans*[15]. The synergistic action of the three antibiotics enhances antibacterial efficacy and may help overcome limitations associated with monotherapy, such as resistance development and incomplete eradication of biofilm-associated pathogens. Additionally, local delivery ensures high drug concentrations at the site of infection with minimal systemic exposure, improving clinical outcomes while reducing side effects[16].

The results from MIC and MBC testing of metronidazole, ciprofloxacin, and minocycline against *Porphyromonas gingivalis*, *Aggregatibacter actinomycetemcomitans*, and *Prevotella intermedia* provide valuable insights into the effectiveness of these agents in periodontal therapy. Each antibiotic exhibited varying degrees of antimicrobial activity, highlighting the necessity of a targeted, multi-drug approach to effectively manage the polymicrobial nature of periodontal infections.

Metronidazole

Metronidazole demonstrated low MIC and MBC values against *Porphyromonas gingivalis* (MIC: 0.03 mg/mL and MBC: 0.12 mg/mL), signifying strong antibacterial activity against this pathogen. The MIC to MBC ratio suggests that Metronidazole acts as a bactericidal agent at low concentrations. However, it showed much higher MIC and MBC values against *Aggregatibacter actinomycetemcomitans* (MIC: 256 mg/mL and MBC: 256 mg/mL), indicating a reduced efficacy against this pathogen. This could be attributed to intrinsic resistance mechanisms or limited activity of Metronidazole against *A. actinomycetemcomitans*. In contrast, *Prevotella intermedia* exhibited high susceptibility to Metronidazole, with both MIC and MBC values at 1

µg/mL, suggesting that Metronidazole is particularly effective against this bacterium.

Ciprofloxacin

Ciprofloxacin exhibited a broad-spectrum activity against all three tested bacterial strains. It showed very low MIC and MBC values for *Aggregatibacter actinomycetemcomitans* (MIC: 0.006 µg/mL, MBC: 0.006 µg/mL), indicating potent bactericidal activity at low concentrations. However, the MIC and MBC for *Porphyromonas gingivalis* were 0.125 µg/mL and 16 µg/mL, respectively, with a significant discrepancy between the two (MIC:MBC ratio of approximately 1:128). This suggests that Ciprofloxacin may function bacteriostatically at low concentrations, requiring higher doses to exert bactericidal effects. Additionally, Ciprofloxacin showed higher MIC and MBC values against *Prevotella intermedia* (MIC: 32 µg/mL and MBC: 32 µg/mL), indicating moderate resistance or decreased susceptibility of this pathogen to Ciprofloxacin.

Minocycline

Minocycline demonstrated strong bactericidal effects against all three pathogens, with low MIC and MBC values across the board. Notably, the MIC and MBC for *Porphyromonas gingivalis* and *Aggregatibacter actinomycetemcomitans* were identical (0.03 µg/mL and 0.12 µg/mL, respectively), suggesting that Minocycline exhibits direct bactericidal activity at low concentrations. Additionally, the MIC and MBC for *Prevotella intermedia* were both 0.016 µg/mL, again indicating robust bactericidal effects. Minocycline stands out as a highly effective antibiotic against all three pathogens tested. A systematic review by do Couto AM and colleagues examined the clinical and radiographic outcomes of pulp revascularization using triple antibiotic paste (TAP) in immature permanent teeth. The analysis of eight studies indicated that TAP was effective in alleviating symptoms and promoting periapical tissue healing in such cases[17].

Vatankhah M et al conducted a systematic review comparing the efficacy of TAP and calcium hydroxide as intracanal medicaments for the treatment of periapical lesions. The findings showed that both agents were effective in supporting lesion

healing; however, TAP demonstrated better outcomes in situations where calcium hydroxide was not sufficient, highlighting its potential role in more resistant infections[18].

In another systematic review, Bains et al investigated the antimicrobial performance of TAP in cases of primary endodontic infection. The review concluded that TAP significantly reduced bacterial load within infected canals. Due to methodological differences across the included studies, a meta-analysis could not be performed, and a qualitative synthesis was presented instead[19]. Valan AS and co-researchers assessed the antimicrobial activity of different formulations and concentrations of TAP—including TAP, TAP hydrogel (TAPH), modified TAP (M-TAP), and M-TAP hydrogel (MTAPH)—against *Enterococcus faecalis*. Their results revealed that M-TAP exhibited superior antibacterial activity compared to conventional TAP, particularly at lower concentrations. The authors recommended using M-TAP at reduced dosages to minimize adverse effects associated with traditional TAP use[20].

Limitations of the Study:

The study was conducted in vitro under controlled laboratory conditions, which do not fully replicate the complex and dynamic environment of the human oral cavity. Additionally, the study did not employ a biofilm model, which is a critical limitation given that periodontal pathogens primarily exist in biofilms in vivo, where they demonstrate increased resistance to antimicrobial agents.

CONCLUSION

The incorporation of all three antibiotics into a single gel formulation enhances the potential of localized periodontal therapy. The triple antibiotic gel acts synergistically to combat a diverse array of periodontal pathogens, reducing the likelihood of resistance and ensuring a more comprehensive antimicrobial effect. This formulation allows for the delivery of high local drug concentrations directly into periodontal pockets, where bacterial load is greatest, while minimizing systemic exposure and associated adverse effects. The gel's ability to effectively target both anaerobic and facultative anaerobic species aligns with the ecological

complexity of the periodontal pocket. By disrupting biofilm formation and eradicating entrenched pathogens, the triple antibiotic gel may significantly improve clinical outcomes, especially in cases resistant to mechanical debridement alone. Thus, this formulation of Triple Antibiotic Paste represents a promising adjunct in the management of periodontitis.

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